

D1.1

PROJECT MANAGEMENT PLAN

Version 2.0

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Abstract

This document is the deliverable “D1.1 – Project Management Plan” of the European project “GRAPHERGIA – Innovative pilot lines for sustainable graphene-based flexible and structural energy harvesting and storage devices” (Grant Agreement number 101120832).

It is a management guide laying down standard workflows and processes for the management activities of GRAPHERGIA project. It will provide guidance and recommendations regarding the organisational structure, the work structure, the quality assurance workflow, the internal communication, the reporting procedure, and the risk assessment mechanisms of the project. The Project Management Plan will foster active collaboration and the smooth implementation of the project.

Keywords

Project management; Communication; Reporting; Quality assurance; Risk management.

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PU Public, fully open. e.g., website

CL Classified information as referred to in Commission Decision 2001/844/EC

CO Confidential to GRAPHERGIA project and Commission Services

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Abbreviations

PMP	Project Management Plan	SC	Steering Committee
EU	European Union	WPL	Work Package Leaders
EC	European Commission	TSL	Task Leaders
WP	Work Package	TL	Team Leaders
PC	Project Coordinator	IRG	Industrial Reference Group
HEU	Horizon Europe	PO	Project Officer
PC	Project Coordinator	PR	Periodic Reports
CA	Consortium Agreement	RP	Reporting Periods
PM	Project Manager	TSLR	Task Leader Report
GA	General Assembly	WPLR	Work Package Leader Report
CSA	Coordination and Support Action	2D	2Dimensional
WG	Working Groups	GFI	Graphene Flagship Initiative
GF	Graphene Flagship		

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document is the deliverable “D1.1 – Project Management Plan” of the European project “GRAPHERGIA – Innovative pilot lines for sustainable graphene-based flexible and structural energy harvesting and storage devices” (Grant Agreement number 101120832).

The GRAPHERGIA Project Management Plan (PMP) is the main document describing how major aspects of the project are planned, managed, monitored, evaluated, and controlled. The PMP describes the procedures and tools that will be used to manage the work plan and work progress, the sharing and storing of documents, the communication between the partners, the quality assessment of the project deliverables, the mitigation measures of any identified risk, and the financial record-keeping.

The PMP will be a living document, updated throughout the project whenever needed. It is delivered in month 2 of the project life, to foster a smooth implementation from the start of the project. The PMP will significantly contribute to the clear definition of the partners’ roles and responsibilities and will help ensure that the project is concluded on time, within budget and with high degree of quality.

This is an updated version (v2.0) of the initial document.

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 OVERVIEW OF THE GRAPHERGIA PROJECT

Despite immense efforts, the world still lacks low-carbon, safe and low-cost energy alternatives to fossil fuels which are responsible for the largest contribution to global climate change. In parallel, the dominance of electric/electronic components in our daily life has enormously increased the demand for sustainable and clean energy production. Harvesting and storage are two critical energy-related processes that have been thoroughly explored over the last decades. On the other hand, the successful isolation of graphene monolayer almost two decades ago has exponentially increased research on graphene and graphene-related materials. To capitalize on the merits of these new carbon nanostructures, the European Union (EU) funded the 1 bn € Graphene Flagship research initiative. Despite the intense efforts, there is still no industrial method able to achieve reliable large-scale production of graphene with consistent and high quality.

GRAPHERGIA proposes to develop a new holistic approach to achieve one-step, laser-assisted synthesis, processing, functionalization and simultaneous integration of graphene-based materials and graphene nanohybrids into relevant energy harvesting/storage devices, leading to a scalable, cost-effective, and climate-neutral production of (i) e-textiles providing wearable power supply and self-powered structural sensors and (ii) next generation electrodes for Li-ion batteries.

GRAPHERGIA is coordinated by the Foundation for Research and Technology, Hellas (FORTH), accompanied by 10 additional partners from 6 European countries, as shown in **Table 1** below:

Number	Short name	Legal name	Country	Logo
1	FORTH	IDRYMA TECHNOLOGIAS KAI EREVNAS	EL	FORTH <small>INSTITUTE OF CHEMICAL ENGINEERING SCIENCES</small>
2	PLE	PLEIONE ENERGY GMBH	DE	PLEIONE <small>ENERGY</small> <small>re-think energy!</small>
3	ADA	ADAMANT AERODIASTIMIKES EFARMOGES	EL	ADAMANT

		ETAIREIA PERIORISMENIS EFTHYNIS		
4	UGE	UNIVERSITE GUSTAVE EIFFEL	FR	
5	Born GmbH	BORN GMBH KNITWEAR FOR FASHION & ENGINEERING	DE	
6	URM	UNIVERSITA DEGLI STUDI DI ROMA LA SAPIENZA	IT	
7	ComS	COMSENSUS, KOMUNIKACIJE IN SENZORIKA, DOO	SI	
8	DLR	DEUTSCHES ZENTRUM FUR LUFT - UND RAUMFAHRT EV	DE	
9	NTT	NEXT TECHNOLOGY TECNOTESSILE SOCIETA NAZIONALE DI RICERCA R L	IT	
10	AUSTRALO	AUSTRALO INTERINNOV MARKETING LAB SL	ES	
11	EUGL	EUGLOTTIA MONOPROSOPI I.K.E.	EL	

Table 1. GRAPHERGIA Consortium

GRAPHERGIA will also subcontract laser-grown graphene electrodes validation to National Physical Laboratory of the United Kingdom.

GRAPHERGIA work plan is broken down in 7 Work Packages (WP) (Table 2). The detailed Gantt chart of the project is included in the Grant Agreement. For the efficient monitoring of the project's progress, GRAPHERGIA foresees 10 milestones, as depicted in Table 3.

WP no	WP name	Lead beneficiary	Start month	End month
1	Scientific Coordination and Project Management	FORTH	1	42
2	Design, development and optimization of textile-based TENGs and micro-flexible SCs	FORTH	1	36
3	LIB cells design and assembly using laser-scribed graphene-based anodes	PLE	6	36
4	Advanced electrical modelling and efficient power management of TENGs for energy harvesting and self-powered sensing IoT applications	UGE	4	36
5	Design, manufacturing and testing of representative technology demonstrators	ADA	6	42
6	Life cycle assessment, sustainability and eco-design approach	NTT	1	42
7	Dissemination, exploitation and communication of project results	AUSTRALO	1	42

Table 2. GRAPHERGIA Work Plan

Milestone no	Milestone name	WP no	Lead beneficiary	Means of Verification	Due Date (month)
1	Laser-processing for proper quality graphene deposition on textiles achieved	WP2, WP6	FORTH	Structure, morphology, and electrical characterization data	18
2	Optimization of flexible SC electrodes accomplished	WP2, WP6	FORTH	Retention of initial performance under stretching washing cycles	24
3	Processing parameters for engineered TENG textile structures in lab-scale assessed	WP2, WP6	FORTH	Materials and processing parameters are documented and evaluated for further up-scaling in pilot scale	24

4	First prototype of plasma-switch with diamond or SiC passivation	WP2, WP4	UGE	Stability of switch ON/OFF actuation voltage over time	24
5	Fabrication of laser-processed electrodes for LIB cells achieved	WP2, WP6	ADA	Electrode mass density, SSA, cyclability, EC properties	24
6	Spice models based on characterization of TENGs and conditioning circuit design	WP4, WP5	UGE	Comparison between simulations-experiments on simple CC	30
7	Integrated energy harvesting and sensory solutions	WP4, WP5	ComS	Capturing / processing / interpreting self-powered TENG sensors	30
8	Prototyping system for TENG-based IoT applications	WP4, WP5	ComS	Operation of embedded system TENG-based IoT applications	33
9	Graphene-based LIB cell benchmarking achieved	WP3, WP5, WP6	PLE	LIB cells perform close to SET plan 2030 targets	36
10	Technology Demonstrator validated	WP5, WP6	ADA	Performance according to Demonstrator KPIs	42

Table 3. GRAPHERGIA Milestones

GRAPHERGIA will ultimately deliver the following Deliverables (**Table 4**).

Deliverable ID	Deliverable name	WP no	Lead beneficiary	Type	Dissemination level (Public or Sensitive)	Due Date (month)
D1.1	Project Management Plan	WP1	FORTH	R	PU	2
D1.2	Data Management Plan	WP1	FORTH	DMP	PU	6
D2.1	Preliminary method for laser-grown graphene films on textiles	WP2	FORTH	R	SEN	18
D2.2	Final method for laser-grown graphene films on textiles	WP2	FORTH	R	SEN	36
D2.3	Preliminary laser-based process for LIB electrodes fabrication	WP2	FORTH	R	SEN	18

D2.4	Final laser-based process for LIB electrodes fabrication	WP2	FORTH	R	SEN	36
D2.5	Preliminary report on electrochemical characterization and performance of microflexible SCs	WP2	DLR	R	SEN	24
D2.6	Final report on electrochemical characterization and performance of microflexible SCs	WP2	DLR	R	SEN	36
D2.7	Preliminary optimized process and QC tools for fluoropolymer-coated textiles	WP2	FORTH	R	SEN	18
D2.8	Final optimized process and QC tools for fluoropolymer-coated textiles	WP2	NTT	R	SEN	33
D3.1	Report on graphene-based LIB cell design and development based on laser-scribed electrodes	WP3	PLE	R	SEN	18
D3.2	Report on aging mechanisms of graphene-based LIB cells	WP3	URM	R	SEN	36
D3.3	Preliminary report on graphene-based LIB cell benchmarking	WP3	PLE	R	SEN	24
D3.4	Final report on graphene-based LIB cell benchmarking	WP3	PLE	R	SEN	36
D4.1	Preliminary optimized CCs circuit for fabricated TENGs	WP4	UGE	R	SEN	15
D4.2	Final optimized CCs circuit for fabricated TENGs	WP4	UGE	R	SEN	24
D4.3	Preliminary energy harvesting system with regulated 3.3 V output based on μ -plasma systems	WP4	UGE	R	PU	18
D4.4	Final energy harvesting system with regulated 3.3 V output based on μ -plasma systems	WP4	UGE	R	PU	33
D4.5	Preliminary method and prototype for capturing / processing / interpreting self-powered TENG sensory systems	WP4	COMS	R	SEN	21
D4.6	Final method and prototype for capturing / processing / interpreting self-powered TENG sensory systems	WP4	COMS	R	SEN	33
D4.7	Modular embedded system for prototyping of TENG-based IoT applications	WP4	COMS	R	SEN	36
D5.1	Preliminary definition of eco-designed based demonstrator development parameters	WP5	NTT	R	SEN	24

D5.2	Final definition of eco-designed based demonstrator development parameters	WP5	NTT	R	SEN	42
D5.3	Prototype for Dem#1 and relevant report	WP5	BORN	DEM	SEN	42
D5.4	Prototype for Dem#2 and relevant report	WP5	ADA	DEM	SEN	42
D5.5	Prototype for Dem#3 and relevant report	WP5	PLE	DEM	SEN	42
D6.1	Preliminary LCA and LCC assessment	WP6	NTT	R	PU	24
D6.2	Final LCA and LCC assessment	WP6	NTT	R	PU	42
D6.3	Preliminary social assessment	WP6	NTT	R	PU	24
D6.4	Final social assessment	WP6	NTT	R	PU	42
D7.1	Plan for the D & E & C of Results (PDEC) - First version	WP7	AUSTRALO	R	PU	6
D7.2	Plan for the D & E & C of Results (PDEC) - Updated version	WP7	AUSTRALO	R	PU	26
D7.3	Plan for the D & E & C of Results (PDEC) - Final version	WP7	AUSTRALO	R	PU	42
D7.4	Preliminary IPR management and exploitation plan	WP7	EUGL	R	SEN	12
D7.5	Final IPR management and exploitation plan	WP7	EUGL	R	SEN	42
D7.6	GRAPHERGIA Best practices handbook	WP7	AUSTRALO	R	PU	42

Table 4. GRAPHERGIA Deliverables

1.2 OBJECTIVE OF THE DELIVERABLE

Deliverable 1.1: “Project Management Plan” is part of WP1. WP1 is organised in 5 tasks, shown below:

- Task 1.1: Technical and Scientific Coordination
- Task 1.2: Project Management, reporting, financial control
- Task 1.3: Contractual documents and EC funding distribution
- Task 1.4: Quality assurance and Risk management
- Task 1.5: Data Management Plan

Deliverable 1.1 is related to tasks 1.1 – 1.4, and is aimed to define and deliver a project management plan which will establish the management and working models to be followed in GRAPHERGIA project regarding the technical, scientific, and financial aspects, the communication within the consortium and with the European Commission (EC), and the project’s reporting, quality assurance and risk management. The establishment of a Data Management Plan will be addressed in Deliverable 1.2.

1.3 DELIVERABLE DESCRIPTION

The deliverable D1.1 is structured in the following chapters:

- Introduction
- Governance structure
- Consortium procedures
- Communication channels
- Workflows
- Risk management
- Conclusions

2 GOVERNANCE STRUCTURE

The governance structure of GRAPHERGIA is outlined in the paragraphs below.

A more extended description of the actors and roles is available in the Grant Agreement and the Consortium Agreement (CA).

2.1 PROJECT COORDINATOR

GRAPHERGIA **Project Coordinator (PC)** is FORTH. The main responsibility of the PC is to ensure the timely and successful progress of the project according to the Grant Agreement. The PC, supported by all partners, will ensure the efficient day-to-day project management, the on-time reporting and the accurate budget monitoring and cost claim. Specifically, the PC will be in charge of: **(a)** acting as the liaison between project partners and Horizon Europe (HEU) representatives on behalf of the consortium and acting as the intermediary for all communications between the beneficiaries and the EC; **(b)** monitoring that the project is implemented properly; **(c)** organising and preparing the project meetings to control the progress of the project; **(d)** monitoring that the project work plan, milestones, and deliverables are in line with the Grant Agreement; **(e)** proposing amendments of the work plan in case of changes in project planning; **(f)** monitoring that gender aspects and ethical issues are addressed appropriately; **(g)** monitoring that the budget is spent in line with the Grant Agreement and elaborating amendments to the budget in case of significant changes in the work plan and timing; **(h)** collecting relevant information (scientific, administrative, financial) and preparing interim and final reports; **(i)** facilitating negotiations in case of defaulting partners; and **(j)** managing the preparation, signature, and maintenance of a CA between the partners.

Project Manager (PM) of GRAPHERGIA is Prof. Spyros Giannopoulos from FORTH, assisted by the General Assembly and the Steering Committee.

2.2 GENERAL ASSEMBLY

The **General Assembly (GA)** is formed by one representative from each partner and chaired by the project coordinator. The GA has the highest decision-making responsibility, will convene annually (but also on an ad hoc basis in case of urgent circumstances) and will ensure the technical and scientific success of the project. FORTH will undertake all necessary initiatives to propose technical solutions and provide scientific and technical guidance whenever necessary. The PC and the GA will also address any ethical issues.

Table 5 below depicts GRAPHERGIA General Assembly composition.

Partner name	Partner representative	Deputy
FORTH	Spyros Yannopoulos	Magda Spella
PLE	Athanasios Masouras	Zambia Kalogridi
ADA	Antonios Vavouliotis	Despoina Batsouli
UGE	Philippe Basset	Armine Karami
Born GmbH	Michael Schneider	Martina Ludwig
URM	Tullio Scopigno	Giovanni Batignani
ComS	Miha Smolnikar	Andrej Campa
DLR	Bilge Saruhan-Brings	Apurba Ray
NTT	Daniele Spinelli	Matteo Maccanti
AUSTRALO	Mona Marill	Vasilis Papanikolaou
EUGL	Konstantinos Vavekis	

Table 5. GRAPHERGIA General Assembly

2.3 STEERING COMMITTEE

The **Steering Committee (SC)** (**Table 6**) is composed by the WP Leaders and chaired by the PC. The WP leaders are FORTH (WP1, WP2), PLE (WP3), UGE (WP4), ADA (WP5), NTT (WP6), AUSTRALO (WP7). The SC will convene every 6 months (but also on an ad hoc basis in case of urgent circumstances). The SC is responsible for the operational day-to-day technical management of the project. Its tasks include taking decisions concerning technical coordination and planning. The SC will also exchange information about the progress in the individual WPs and, in terms of risk management, see how potential problems or delays in one WP might have an influence on the other tasks or WP(s). In addition, the SC shall be responsible for the proper execution and implementation of the decisions of the General Assembly.

Work Package	Partner name	Representative	Deputy
1	FORTH	Spyros Yannopoulos	Magda Spella
2	FORTH	Spyros Yannopoulos	Michail Athanasiou
3	PLE	Athanasios Masouras	Zambia Kalogridi
4	ADA	Antonios Vavouliotis	Despoina Batsouli
5	UGE	Philippe Basset	Armine Karami
6	NTT	Daniele Spinelli	Matteo Maccanti
7	AUSTRALO	Mona Marill	Laura Argiles

Table 6. GRAPHERGIA Steering Committee

2.4 WORK PACKAGE LEADERS

The **Work Package Leaders (WPL)** are responsible for managing the tasks grouped in the Work Packages. The WPL report to the SC, ensuring the timely fulfilment of duties from a scientific and technical point of view. The WPLs assure the coordination between the different project teams and assume the role of an interface between the partners of their WP and the PC.

WPL ensure the timely execution of tasks included in each WP, by stimulating the interaction between the various partners involved and coordinating the workflow. They are also in charge of the consolidation of the reports, they will keep the SC informed about the development, progress, and status of their WP on a regular basis and they will ensure the timely submission of deliverables relating to their WP in cooperation with the lead beneficiary of the deliverable.

2.5 TASK LEADERS

The **Task Leaders (TSL)** are responsible for the timely and efficient implementation of their specific task and the coordination with the other tasks of the WP. They report to the WPL in case of any deviation or risk. TSL are also responsible for the preparation of the deliverables resulting from their tasks and the coordination with other tasks for their participation in the deliverable preparation, and for the preparation and delivery of internal task progress reports to the WPL.

2.6 TEAM LEADERS

To facilitate an efficient communication process between the partners, a **Team Leader (TL)** and deputy (if applicable) are appointed by every partner (Table 7). The TL is the partner institution's spokesperson. The TL act as the interface between the working team at their institution and the WPL as well as the consortium. They are responsible for keeping the WPL informed about the development, progress, and status of their institution's work in a WP and will ensure the timely

submission of the deliverables of their institution and their report to the WPL during periodic and internal reporting.

The TL are also responsible for keeping their team informed about anything that is happening in the consortium. This means that all relevant project information channelled from the PC should be distributed by the TL to their entire team, if required.

Partner name	Partner representative	Partner deputy
FORTH	Spyros Yannopoulos	Magda Spella, Michail Athanasiou
PLE	Athanasios Masouras	Zambia Kalogridi
ADA	Antonios Vavouliotis	Despoina Batsouli
UGE	Philippe Basset	Armine Karami
Born GmbH	Michael Schneider	Martina Ludwig
URM	Tullio Scopigno	Giovanni Batignani
ComS	Miha Smolnikar	Andrej Campa
DLR	Apurba Ray	Bilge Saruhan-Brings
NTT	Daniele Spinelli	Matteo Maccanti
AUSTRALO	Mona Marill	Vasilis Papanikolaou
EUGL	Konstantinos Vavekis	

Table 7. GRAPHERGIA Team Leaders

2.7 INDUSTRIAL REFERENCE GROUP

GRAPHERGIA has established an **Industrial Reference Group (IRG)** (Table 8) to ensure maximum benefit from the scientific, technological and innovation results of the project. This will be achieved by systematically disseminating information to the European industry and relevant stakeholders. This communication channel established with stakeholders from various categories, is also important to: (i) influence the project to achieve maximum industrial benefit of the results through feedback during implementation, and (ii) estimate the benefit that can be achieved in the European industry through the products and services developed within the project. Among the IRG roles is to guide GRAPHERGIA by providing product specifications, market trends and priorities. For this reason, members of the IRG will be invited to participate in WP meetings, to gain knowledge of the work progress and provide their valuable feedback for the efficient steering of the project. The members of the IRG have already agreed upon their role in GRAPHERGIA, expressing their strong interest in guiding product development.

Enterprise	Contact person	Particular interstate in GRAPHERGIA R&I activities
Siemens	Franzika Wiebels	Potential application of project products in power tools
ESA	Dr. Ugo Lafont	Graphene-based LIB cells for space industry applications
Rolls-Royce plc	Dr. Ch. Argyrakis	Self-powered structurally integrated sensors
EasyMotionSkin	Ralf Kahlenberg	Adoption of products for wearables integration into clothing
Würth Electronics	Dr. Alina Schreivogel	Potential application of LIB cells in electric components
NPL	Dr. Cristina Giusca	Metrology and validation of laser-grown graphene on textiles
CSA Graphene Flagship	Jackie Brown	Contribution to the governance and coordination of Graphene Flagship initiative
Hyperion Investing	George Malandrakis	Investing in green energy and digital transition technologies

Table 8. GRAPHERGIA Industrial Reference Group

3 CONSORTIUM PROCEDURES

3.1 DECISION MAKING

Day-to-day technical and administrative decisions within the project are taken by the PC. Strategic decisions and major technical and operational decisions (like any reschedule of deliverables, milestones, tasks, effort) are taken by the GA.

The GA will deliberate and make decisions validly only if two-thirds (2/3) of its members are present or represented (quorum). Each member shall have one vote. Defaulting parties may not vote. In case of conflict resolution voting, a majority of 80% is required. The PC mediates and participates in all important decision. Decisions will only be binding once the relevant part of the minutes has been accepted.

The PC will produce written minutes of each meeting and send them to all partners within 10 calendar days of the meeting. The minutes will be the formal record of all decisions taken and will be considered as accepted if, within 10 calendar days from sending, no member has sent an objection in writing to the PC with respect to the accuracy of the minutes. The PC will send the accepted minutes to all the members of the GA and the SC.

Exercise of veto: Any member of GRAPHERGIA has the right to exercise a veto when it recognises that it is affected by a decision of the GA or the SC. When the decision is foreseen in the original agenda, a member may veto such a decision during the meeting only. When a decision has been taken on a new item added to the agenda before or during the meeting, a member may veto such decision during the meeting and within 15 days after the draft minutes of the meeting are sent. In case of exercise of veto, the members shall make every effort to resolve the matter which occasioned the veto to the general satisfaction of all members. A defaulting party can't exercise a veto. A party requesting to leave the consortium may not veto decisions relating to that.

3.2 CONFLICT MANAGEMENT

In case of conflicts arising within the consortium, the following steps will be taken:

- ❑ The parties will first try to resolve the conflict amicably between them.
- ❑ If a conflict cannot be resolved in this way, it is raised to the PC; for conflict resolution in a technical aspect, the PC is responsible for proposing an alternative. If this is agreed, the issue is solved.
- ❑ If this attempt fails, the issue will be brought to the GA and the PC will try to solve it by consensus. The GA will decide which procedure will be followed and the corresponding correction measures that should be taken. The partner causing the conflict will declare acceptance of the procedure and the corrective measures.
- ❑ If the conflict cannot be resolved, the PC declares the participant “not in line” with the project execution and the consortium will ask for a contract termination for the partner concerned, with the contractually stated consequences. The Project Officer (PO) will be immediately notified of the situation and of the measures that have been taken. An appropriate review of the work plan will be suggested by the PC, approved by the GA and sent to the EC for acceptance.
- ❑ In case it is decided (by the PC or the GA) that a conflict resolution will involve a voting procedure among partners, a majority of the 80% will be required for the decision to go ahead.

3.3 QUALITY MANAGEMENT

The quality assurance methodologies of the project will be coordinated by the PC and the WPL. General quality policies to be followed include:

- ❑ Compliance of each result, deliverable and milestone to the work plan, the Grant Agreement and the approved budget.
- ❑ Respect of deadlines for activities and deliverables.
- ❑ Deliverables shall be checked and reviewed before submission by the consortium.

- ❑ Each partner will record their activities (technical, financial, dissemination, communication) and report them on time for the internal and official reporting procedures.
- ❑ Any delays or quality problems will be reported as soon as possible to the PC.

To check the quality of WP activities, deliverables, and milestones the main **performance indicators** will be:

- ❑ Monitoring of the activity plan and deadlines (to be checked through the detailed GANTT)
- ❑ Relevance of the outcomes
- ❑ Achievement of the goals and objectives
- ❑ Adjustment procedures

3.4 ETHICS MANAGEMENT

The PC and the GA will be responsible for maintaining the ethics roadmap of GRAPHERGIA. Their general responsibilities include:

- ❑ Checking for compliance with ethical standards within the relevant research fields.
- ❑ Reporting the progress of how the ethical issues are addressed in the project.
- ❑ Ensuring gender equality in all activities of the project.
- ❑ Ensuring alignment with the Data Protection Authorities of the involved Member States, aimed at demonstrating the compliance of the ethics, privacy and data protection processes with the European and national legal framework.
- ❑ Collecting free and fully informed consent (where applicable).
- ❑ Where applicable, providing to the EC further detailed information on the source of the data, privacy/confidentiality, and the procedures that will be implemented for data collection, storage, access, sharing policies, protection, retention and destruction.

FORTH has an established Research Ethics Committee (<https://www.forth.gr/en/content/Ethics-Committee.122/>) and a Gender Equality and Discrimination Committee (<https://archive.forth.gr/EIF/index-en.html>) and will guide the ethics assessment activities of the project.

3.5 COST MANAGEMENT

Cost Management refers to the process of gathering, monitoring, and managing the financial resources throughout the project's life cycle. This means that accurate and actual data should be maintained and updated accordingly by all partners.

The project budget reflects the estimated eligible costs, that GRAPHERGIA partners need in order to perform the project activities and is detailed in the overall project budget in the Grant Agreement.

For efficient cost management, the PC will request a financial internal report every 6-7 months, where real personnel costs, other direct costs and indirect costs during the period will be indicated. Each partner is responsible to control their costs in accordance with their own accounting and management practices. The PC will then check for any significant deviation between actual and planned costs; if so, corrective actions are defined and put in place. This procedure will enable rapid response and mitigation to potential progress or cost impacts before they become milestone impacts.

4 COMMUNICATION CHANNELS

Efficient and continuous communication is essential for the success of GRAPHERGIA. The communication occurs at different levels in the project:

- ❑ Communication within the consortium
- ❑ Communication with the PO and the EC
- ❑ Communication with the external stakeholders
- ❑ Communication with GrapheneEU

The following general communication rules are defined in GRAPHERGIA:

- ❑ All communication regarding any issue or problem should be directed to the PC (Spyros Yannopoulos, Magda Spella).
- ❑ Only the PC will communicate with the PO and send documents or information. The partners should not directly contact the PO themselves.
- ❑ The PC will also take on the main communication role with the consortium with regard to the distribution of meeting material, minutes, agenda, information regarding upcoming deliverables, follow-up, information about reporting procedures, contractual issues and any other relevant information or communication.

4.1 INTERNAL COMMUNICATION

For the communication between all the partners of the consortium, several internal communication channels and tools are at the consortium's disposal, such as:

- ❑ GRAPHERGIA Teamspace on Graphene Flagship Initiative (GFI) Onboard space
- ❑ Slack Workspace
- ❑ Contact list and emails
- ❑ Project meetings

In general, all communication regarding any issue or problem should be directed to the PC (Spyros Yannopoulos, Magda Spella), who will take final decisions. All partners are encouraged to discuss openly and alert to issues/problems as early as possible.

To ensure consistency across the activities of GRAPHERGIA, the following templates have been developed: (a) Deliverable template; (b) Document template; (c) PowerPoint presentation template; (d) GRAPHERGIA logo.

Document names

To allow easy tracking and retrieval of project documents a systematic approach will be used.

Each document name will start with the date (in reverse order) on which the document was sent and/or released.

Names of deliverables will be given according to the following structure:

- Date of document_GRAPHERGIA_Deliverable number_Deliverable title_draft/final
- Example: 231130_GRAPHERGIA_D1.1_Project Management Plan_final

Naming of other documents will be given according to the following structure:

- Date of document_GRAPHERGIA_Main topic of document
- Example: 231130_GRAPHERGIA_Deliverable template

4.1.1 GRAPHERGIA Teamspace

The Graphene Flagship (Graphene EU) (GF) has set up a collaborative space (GFI Onboard) where all projects under the GFI have a private space to share news, events, documents, useful information, research outputs, etc.

GRAPHERGIA Teamspace features the following tabs: News, Research Outputs, Project Members, Documents, Deliverables, Events. GRAPHERGIA uses this teamspace to share and communicate dissemination and communication activities, news of the project and of the Graphene Flagship, interesting upcoming (scientific and other) events, open deliverables, new results (Figure 1). All partners have access to the teamspace to upload and share their content.

The screenshot shows the GRAPHERGIA Teamspace interface. At the top, there is a teal banner with the text "Welcome to GRAPHERGIA's Teamspace". Below this, the main content area is divided into three sections: a large graphic on the left with the text "GRAPHERGIA: Innovative pilot lines for sustainable graphene-based flexible..." and a "Learn more" link, a "Kick-Off meeting" button, and a "Quick links" section on the right. The "Quick links" section includes links to the GRAPHERGIA public website, GRAPHERGIA @ X (Twitter), GRAPHERGIA @ LinkedIn, GRAPHERGIA @ YouTube, and two links for learning how to add a news post and a page. On the left side, there is a sidebar with navigation options in Greek: Αρχική, Δημιουργία, Λεπτομέρειες σελίδας, Ανάλυση, Pages, News, Research Outputs, Project Members, Documents, Deliverables, Events, Site contents, Κάδος Ανακύκλωσης, and Επεξεργασία.

Figure 1. GRAPHERGIA Teamspace on GFI Onboard

4.1.2 GRAPHERGIA Slack Workspace

The partner AUSTRALO, leader of communication and dissemination of the project and WPL of WP7, has also set up a GRAPHERGIA Slack Workspace. Slack is a collaborative cross-platform team communication tool. GRAPHERGIA partners will be able to communicate through text messages, file and media sharing, voice and video calls in private chats or within designated communities called "channels."

4.1.3 Contact lists and e-mails

- ❑ The following mailing lists have been created to facilitate communication between the partners:
 - GRAPHERGIA-all, reaching all people working in GRAPHERGIA
 - GRAPHERGIA-core, reaching GRAPHERGIA Work Package leaders
 - GRAPHERGIA-general assembly, reaching GRAPHERGIA General Assembly members
 - GRAPHERGIA-management, reaching FORTH's management team

Each partner is obliged to send any changes regarding the contact persons immediately to the PC, so that the mailing list is updated.

- ❑ The following contact lists have been created:
 - All GRAPHERGIA partners

- GRAPHERGIA General Assembly
- GRAPHERGIA Steering Committee
- GRAPHERGIA Partner Team leaders
- GRAPHERGIA PC Management team

Each partner is obliged to send any changes regarding the contact persons immediately to the PC, so that the mailing list is updated and circulated to the other partners.

- The subject field of the e-mails should contain the following components:
[GRAPHERGIA] - Main topic of mail

Example: [GRAPHERGIA] - Minutes of Meeting 02.11.2023

- The main addressee of the e-mail should be the responsible person to take action as a consequence of the e-mail. Persons who are put in copy (CC:) are generally not expected to take action. Dates or deadlines should be included if needed. If no reply is provided within the deadline, the ‘silence is approval’ principle will be applied.
- When answering e-mails sent to all consortium members, partners should generally not make use of the “reply to all” function unless this is required following the purpose of the e-mail. Answers should only be directed to the partners concerned in order to keep project-related e-mails to a manageable number.

4.1.4 Project meetings

GRAPHERGIA partners have agreed during the project Kick-off Meeting to the following meetings schedule:

- **GRAPHERGIA onsite progress meetings:** Project progress meetings will bring together the entire consortium approximately every 9 months. The meetings will last approximately 1.5 days. The agenda will generally include a session on the progress of the workplan, a management session, a risk assessment session and other topics, if any, relevant at certain points in the project. If needed, the hosting institution will make sure that a hybrid connection is available for those partners that cannot attend the meeting physically. If the situation requires it, project progress meetings may also be held completely remotely. At least one representative from each partner should attend the meetings. In case of absence, the partners should inform the PC in advance. The venue of the progress meetings will be discussed and agreed with all the partners. These meetings will be initiated by the PC, together with the partner hosting the meeting in their premises. Meetings’ minutes will be prepared by the PC and sent to all the partners.
- **GRAPHERGIA online progress meetings:** GRAPHERGIA consortium will meet remotely every 2 months (even months) to monitor the progress of the workplan, the status of deliverables and milestones, and the risk assessment. For these meetings, the WPL will prepare a short

presentation on the status of their WP (work progress as well as quality assurance and risk management); all partners are therefore required to send to their WPL any results/data/risks well in advance. At least one representative from each partner should attend the meetings. In case of absence, the partners should inform the PC in advance. Should issues arise, online meetings will be scheduled among the partners concerned to discuss further details. These meetings will be initiated by the PC. Meetings' minutes will be prepared by the PC and sent to all the partners.

- ❑ **GRAPHERGIA WP online meetings:** Dedicated WP meetings will be organised every 2 months (odd months), so that the progress of each technical WP is more efficiently monitored. These meetings will be initiated by the WPL. Meetings' minutes will be prepared by the WPL and sent to all the partners working in the WP.
- ❑ **Members of GRAPHERGIA Steering Committee** will interact frequently through e-mails and will set up virtual meetings on demand to follow the project's progress. Meetings' minutes will be prepared by the PC and sent to all members of the SC.
- ❑ Meetings between individual partners will be handled by the partners as the need arises. Meetings' minutes will be sent to the WPL and the PC.

To ensure homogeneous formatting across all GRAPHERGIA presentations, AUSTRALO has prepared a "GRAPHERGIA PowerPoint Presentation Template", already uploaded on the GRAPHERGIA Teamspace and internal repository.

4.2 COMMUNICATION WITH THE PO AND THE EC

The communication with the EC will be achieved through the communication of the PC with the Project Officer Mr. Patrick Bourrel. The main communication channels will include (a) e-mails; (b) the SEDIA (Single Electronic Data Interchange Area) portal; (c) online meetings.

4.3 COMMUNICATION WITH EXTERNAL STAKEHOLDERS

The communication of the project to the external stakeholders is the subject of Deliverables D7.1, D7.2 and D7.3 (First, Updated and Final Plans respectively for the Dissemination & Exploitation & Communication of Results), to be submitted in months 6, 26, and 42 of the project.

4.4 COMMUNICATION WITH GRAPHENE EU

The Graphene Flagship initiative aims at advancing Europe's strategic autonomy in technologies that rely on graphene and other 2Dimensional (2D) materials; this overarching goal will be accomplished through several graphene and 2D materials related actions. GrapheneEU is the Coordination and Support Action (CSA) project that aims to guarantee the coherence of the GFI, allowing the separate actions to exploit synergies in their scientific and technological activities and work more efficiently by utilising common services and support functions.

GRAPHERGIA has dedicated Task7.4 to the collaboration with GrapheneEU. GRAPHERGIA will contribute to the following Work Packages and Working Groups (WG) of GrapheneEU:

- ❑ GrapheneEU WP1 Coordination and Governance: GRAPHERGIA will contribute to the common governance structure of the GFI via the participation in the “Coordination Board” Working Group as well as in a regular Science and Technology Forum contributing to common reporting of project outputs. GRAPHERGIA is represented by Prof. Spyros Yannopoulos.
- ❑ GrapheneEU WP2 European and international alignment: GRAPHERGIA, through Prof. Spyros Yannopoulos, participates in the association mechanism by providing support for the integration of associate members and partnering projects within the GFI, by participating in the network of national and thematic representatives and ensuring active representation and contribution of the 2D material research community in major initiatives. GRAPHERGIA supports 2 Partnering Projects and 4 Associated Members so far.
- ❑ GrapheneEU WP3 Dissemination: GRAPHERGIA will provide a representative (Ms. Mona Marill) to the “Dissemination” Working Group to align on key messages and common actions, contribute to a common website and support in the creation of the annual Graphene Week conference and other joint events while contributing to the central GF events calendar with workshops, exhibitions, etc, where possible.

More in detail, the specific objective of the “Dissemination” WG is to share efforts in promoting graphene-related projects, including GRAPHERGIA, and making the best use of the results among the target stakeholders. GRAPHERGIA will participate in joint events, the Graphene Week, workshops and webinars, and will widen its stakeholders' ecosystem thanks to the well-established GF community that has been built in the last 10 years. GRAPHERGIA will perform joint communication of GrapheneEU on its website (cross-referencing GrapheneEU website <https://graphene-flagship.eu/>), on its social media (LinkedIn, X & Youtube) and its media outlets (press releases, newsletters, etc.). GRAPHERGIA will also be showcased in GrapheneEU publications, for instance, in the Graphene Flagship Annual Reports.

To plan and monitor the work of the WG, Ms. Mona Marill, GRAPHERGIA WP7 leader, already participates in the regular online WG meetings.

- ❑ GrapheneEU WP4 Industrialisation support: GRAPHERGIA will contribute to the GrapheneEU “Standardisation Activities” Working Group by conducting a value-chain-based roadmap on GRAPHERGIA’s core topics, by coordinating standardisation activities, and by supporting innovation both within the project and within the GF innovation activities. Part of this WG is also the discussions about the REACH/ECHA committee. GRAPHERGIA is represented by Prof. Spyros Yannopoulos.
- ❑ GrapheneEU has also set up a Project Management Network (PMN) Working Group, bringing together the administrative managers of all Graphene Flagship projects, in order to facilitate the coordinated implementation and governance of all projects. The PMN meets regularly,

fostering the exchange of good management practices. GRAPHERGIA is represented by Ms Magda Spella.

All the above will contribute to formulating specific policy recommendations and standardization reports, further improving the GRAPHERGIA Best Practices Handbook.

Apart from the participation to the above working groups:

- GrapheneEU contact person Ms. Jackie Brown attended online the GRAPHERGIA kick-off meeting (2-3 November 2023), presented the GrapheneEU project and laid out the routes of collaboration between the two projects.
- Members of GRAPHERGIA attended the common kick-off meeting of all GF projects (5-6 February 2024 in Gothenburg, Sweden).
- GRAPHERGIA PM Prof. S. Yannopoulos has attended all the online sessions hosted by GrapheneEU regarding the forthcoming Innovative Materials Partnership (IM4EU).
- GRAPHERGIA attended the GF 2024 Annual Meeting.

5 WORKFLOWS

5.1 DELIVERABLE WORKFLOW

To guarantee the timely submission of deliverables that meet the quality requirements of the EC, a formal quality control process will be followed in GRAPHERGIA project, as shown in the following **Figure 2**:

Figure 2. GRAPHERGIA Deliverable Quality Control Plan

To ensure homogeneous formatting and content across all GRAPHERGIA Deliverables, AUSTRALO has prepared a “GRAPHERGIA Deliverable Template”, which is uploaded on GRAPHERGIA Teamspace and internal repository. The deliverable should be a self-contained document, which can be understood without knowledge of the DoA. In short, all GRAPHERGIA Deliverables should cover the following topics:

- ❑ Front page
- ❑ Version history
- ❑ Table of contents
- ❑ Lists of figures and tables
- ❑ Executive summary
- ❑ Introduction - Description
- ❑ Objectives. The objectives of the deliverable should be clearly stated.
- ❑ Cohesive and concise content, consistent with the description in the DoA; any deviations from the DoA should be explained. Links to other deliverables, if applicable.

- ❑ Conclusions
- ❑ Possible Annexes

The final version of the deliverables must be submitted to the PC in Word and pdf formats and will be available in the GRAPHERGIA repository. If finally approved, GRAPHERGIA public deliverables will be published via the project web site.

5.1.1 Deliverables quality management

Once a deliverable is completed by the lead beneficiary, it will go through a review process as well as a quality check according to the checklist presented in **Table 9** below. All deliverables will be checked by the PC and the WPL. Members of the IRG may also be invited to review GRAPHERGIA deliverables when relevant, especially for the demo cases.

Quality Indicator	Checklist
Accordance with the objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❑ Detailed description of work and activities ❑ Relevance of content
Respect of the templates and visual identity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❑ Visual identity rules (project logo, EU emblem, funding disclaimer, to be detailed in Deliverable 7.1)
Clarity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❑ Concise and understandable language and content <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❑ Consistent document structure ❑ Correct use of figures, tables and diagrams <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❑ Accordance with standards ❑ Clarity of arguments
Completeness	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❑ Completeness of information (missing topics, references, parts, etc.)

Table 9. GRAPHERGIA Deliverable Quality Checklist

5.1.2 Deliverables risk management

All partners are expected to do their best to ensure that GRAPHERGIA deliverables are submitted on time.

All partners are also expected to notify immediately and well in advance the WPL and the PC in case a significant delay in the submission of the delivery is foreseen. When it becomes apparent that a deliverable will not be delivered on time, the lead beneficiary must immediately inform the PC and the WPL about **(a)** the reason of the delay; **(b)** the impact on the work plan; **(c)** the impact on resources and budget; **(d)** the mitigation actions; **(e)** the new due date. In this way, an official

postponement of the deliverable will be negotiated with the EC. Cases of unjustified delays or of delays for which no proactive notification was given should be avoided.

This established process will ensure that all GRAPHERGIA deliverables are well-written, well-structured and of excellent quality.

5.2 MEETINGS ORGANISATION WORKFLOW

Physical meeting preparations will be a joint effort of the hosting institution and the PC. The time and place of every physical meeting will be pre-approved by all partners.

The hosting institution should take care of the following aspects when organising a physical meeting:

- Finding a venue for the meeting.
- Provide to the other partners a list of convenient hotels, travel information, all necessary addresses, etc.
- Organise coffee and lunch breaks during the meeting, and propose a location for the project dinner.

The PC will take care of the following aspects of the meeting:

- Prepare the meeting materials (agenda, attendance list) and keep minutes
- Coordinate dissemination material

5.3 REPORTING WORKFLOW

There will be two kinds of report in GRAPHERGIA:

- Periodic Reports** to be submitted to the EC.
- Internal Progress Reports** to be submitted to the PC.

The reporting process is summarised in the next **Figure 3**.

Figure 3. GRAPHERGIA Reporting Plan

5.3.1 Periodic Reports

Three official Periodic Reports (PR) are anticipated in GRAPHERGIA, following the end of each of the three Reporting Periods (RP):

- ❑ RP 1: From M1 to M18
- ❑ RP 2: From M19 to M30
- ❑ RP 3: From M31 to M42

The PRs will be organised by the PC who will request the necessary contributions from the partners. The PC must submit the technical and financial reports to the EC within 60 days following the end of each RP, according to the Articles 21 and 22 of the Grant Agreement, including requests for payment, and using the forms and templates provided in the electronic exchange system. The PRs are structured in the following 2 parts:

Periodic technical report: It describes the technical work carried out by the partners, containing an overview of the progress towards the objectives of the action, including results, milestones, deliverables, critical risks-deviations from the action, dissemination/exploitation/communication activities, intellectual property rights, economic and societal impact assessment, follow-up recommendations and comments from previous review(s) (if applicable), and a summary for publication by the EC. One part of the report is automatically assembled by the Continuous Reporting tabs of the SyGMA portal.

Periodic financial report: It includes an individual financial statement and an explanation of the use of resources from each partner for the reporting period concerned.

The methodology for the periodic reporting progress is depicted in the following **Table 10**:

What	Who	How	Deadline
GRAPHERGIA SyGMA platform updated	ALL, coordinated by the PC	Enter all relevant information in the tabs of the Continuous Reporting system	Continuous
Team Leaders Report (TLR)	TL	Report all implemented activities. Designated template available	2 weeks after the end of the reporting period
Task Leader Report (TSLR)	TSL	Compile the TLreports. Designated template available	4 weeks after the end of the reporting period
Work Package Leader Report (WPLR)	WPL	Compile the TSLR. Designated template available	6 weeks after the end of the reporting period
Technical Periodic Report	PC	Final report based on the WPLR	2 days before submission deadline
Financial Periodic Report	ALL, via SyGMA portal	Enter and finalise financial data	2 weeks before submission day
Submission of the final Periodic Report (scientific + financial part)	PC	Via SyGMA portal	2 days before submission deadline

Table 10. GRAPHERGIA Reporting Methodology

The deadlines, including precise dates for the delivery of the individual reports, will be communicated by the PC shortly before the beginning of the reporting. The PC will provide support in any aspect relating to the reporting, including advice for financial reporting.

5.3.2 Internal reporting

The internal reporting process, regarding technical progress and resources consumption, will be carried out in the middle of every reporting period (**Figure 3**) and according to the plan presented in **Table 10**. The objectives of this internal reporting process are:

- (1) to detect any deviation or problem or risk and to act consequently
- (2) to solve any conflict / doubt that may arise among partners

The internal reporting process will be done using an easy to fill excel file to gather the next information about each partner:

- Summary table of the human resources (measured as person-months) dedicated to each WP.
- Explanation of the activities carried out in each WP.

- ❑ Profile of the people working on the project (name, gender, professional category, etc.).
- ❑ Incurred costs and other financial issues

The PC will distribute this excel file to all the Team Leaders and will notify them about the deadline of delivery.

6 RISK MANAGEMENT

Risk Management is the identification, assessment, and prioritisation of risks to minimize, monitor and control the probability and/or impact of unfortunate events. Since not all risks can be eliminated, mitigation strategies and contingency plans can be developed to lessen their impact if they occur. The continuous internal reporting process and the (at least) 2-monthly WP meetings foreseen in GRAPHERGIA, will help ensure that any unexpected challenge, problem or risk can be identified promptly.

The Risk Management activities of GRAPHERGIA will attempt to decrease the probability and impact of negative events by identifying and planning for risks before significant negative consequences occur that can jeopardise the accomplishment of the committed objectives of the project. All activities related with the risk management are monitored by the PM in collaboration with the WPL.

The risk management procedure in the GRAPHERGIA project follows the steps shown in **Figure 4**:

Figure 4. GRAPHERGIA Risk Management Plan

1. Risk identification: Any partner in the consortium may identify risks. The risks may be identified during the execution of any activity of the project, during the internal technical reporting process or during the project-meetings. There are four categories or types of risks:

- ❑ Implementation risks, related to technical factors.
- ❑ Financial risks, related to unexpected situations affecting the financial capacity of the partners.
- ❑ Intellectual Property risks.
- ❑ Management and administrative risks.

Risk identification is an iterative process. The first phase of risk identification occurred during the preparation of the proposal; since the beginning of the project, some key risks to be kept monitored have already been identified and listed in the Grant Agreement.

2. Risk evaluation and prioritisation: Evaluating a risk involves establishing values for its potential effect on scope, cost and/or schedule of the project. A determination is made as to the:

- Probability (likelihood) of the risk occurring (low / medium / high).
- Ability to mitigate the risk.
- Potential impact of the risk (low / medium / high).

The combination of probability and impact is used to evaluate the risk level (Low, Medium or High) and to get a list of the prioritised risks.

3. Risk mitigation plan. Based on the previous step, the PC, the WPL and the TSL will define a risk response for each risk. Such responses can be aimed at handling the risk if it occurs, at trying to avoid the risk, at reducing the impact of the risk, at closely monitoring the risk, or at determining contingency actions to be taken once the risk has occurred. As a rule, the risk response plans will be drafted with the occasion of the internal progress reports (every 9-10 months), unless an urgent action is required. The selected strategies require approval by the GRAPHERGIA Steering Committee before being applied.

4. Risk monitoring and control. Risk monitoring is the process of keeping track of the risks and evaluating the effectiveness of the response actions. Monitoring is done in a continuous manner, and it may provide a basis for developing additional response actions and identifying new risks. The PC, the WPL and the TSL will review the effectiveness of risk responses, re-analyse existing risks, review project performance and evaluate the effectiveness of the risk management process.

7 CONCLUSIONS

This deliverable provides guidance in the daily work of the GRAPHERGIA consortium and should be consulted by all project beneficiaries to facilitate an efficient and effective work process. It provides the necessary insights into the organization structure, the work structure, the reporting procedure and the risk management. The document will be updated on a frequent basis, taking into account the most recent and relevant changes.